

**INCLUSIVE EDUCATION IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN
DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS**

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Abstract: *The article presents the results of monitoring international and national projects on the introduction of inclusive education in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The results of sociological studies at various intervals allow us to assess the readiness of society for the further development of inclusive education in Uzbekistan.*

Key Words: *Inclusive education, people with disabilities, secondary schools, integration.*

As we know, inclusive education is such a learning process in which all children, regardless of their physical, mental, intellectual, cultural, ethnic, linguistic and other characteristics, are included in the general education system by their peers without disabilities in the same general education schools. In such general schools that take into account their special educational needs and provide their students with the necessary special support. While integrated learning takes place in a joint educational environment of children with disabilities and children who do not have such disabilities, by providing children with disabilities with special conditions for learning and social adaptation that do not reduce the overall level of education for children, do not having such restrictions in the class.

According to the current Law "On Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan", the term "inclusive education" is characterized by the provision of equal access to education for all persons, taking into account personal characteristics and special educational needs.

Currently, there are 710,000 people with disabilities in the Republic of Uzbekistan, of which 101,316 are children with disabilities.

In 2006-2009, the Ministry of Education, with the support of the Asian Development Bank, implemented the project "General Education for

Children with Disabilities", within which 38 schools, boarding schools were selected, of which 22 specialized and 16 general education, in Tashkent, Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya regions. All schools have been reconstructed and renovated in order to provide all the amenities for children with special needs. The results of a sociological study conducted during the period of this project showed that 58% of parents of children with disabilities are against teaching their child in a partner school, 30% conditionally agree, 3% look positively. However, as a result of a survey of children with disabilities, an average of 66% expressed a desire to study in a general education school, a survey of children without disabilities showed a desire of ordinary children to study together by 77%. The results of the survey indicate that it is not the interaction of children that leads to the segregation of children with disabilities from mainstream schools, but the attitudes of adults and their prejudices regarding disability, which ultimately create barriers for children with disabilities to study in mainstream educational schools.

Since 2017, the Republican Center for Social Adaptation of Children has been implementing the fundamental project BF-1-001 "Creating a system of high-quality, continuous inclusive education in the Republic of Uzbekistan", as a result of the project, monitoring of children involved in inclusive education was carried out.

Based on the results of the monitoring of inclusive education in the pilot regions, it was revealed that: all teachers in the pilot institutions have information about inclusive education; experience difficulties in teaching children in the classroom due to the lack of a sufficient number of teaching aids, literature on working on the psychological and speech activity of children with special needs; all children studying in inclusive classes are admitted to school on the conclusion of the MPPC; the attitude towards students who develop normally and their parents towards students with special learning needs is positive.

Thus, in order to form in students and teachers a kind of inclusive culture and competencies necessary for effective and inclusive work, the issues of inclusive education should be more widely informed in the media through seminars and trainings for teachers and students.

LITERATURE:

1. Law "On Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan", the term "inclusive education" (registration No. 2685 of 06/17/2015).

2. Grinina E. S. The attitude of student youth to persons with disabilities // News of the Saratov University. New series. Acmeology of education. Psychology of development. 2015. T 4. Issue. 4 (16). pp. 333–337.

3. Muminova L.R., Uzakova Z.F. Experience of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the transition to inclusive education. Journal/Inclusion in education. Volume 4, No. 2, 2019

4. Chicherina Ya.E., Bondareva E.V. Studying the conditions and factors for the introduction of inclusive education in the Republic of Uzbekistan. T.: 2008 p.36
